

Article type: Review

Title:

A systematic review of deep learning models trained and tested using the HAM10000 dataset: an overview of recent advancements and challenges

Gokul Srinivasan¹; Jason McFadden¹; Yunrui Lu, MS³; Matthew J. Davis, MD²; Joshua J. Levy, PhD^{1,2,3,4,5,*}

- 1) Dartmouth College, Hanover, NH
- 2) Department of Dermatology, Dartmouth-Hitchcock Medical Center, Lebanon, NH
- 3) Department of Epidemiology, Dartmouth College Geisel School of Medicine, Hanover, NH
- 4) Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Dartmouth-Hitchcock Medical Center, Lebanon, NH
- 5) Program in Quantitative Biomedical Sciences, Dartmouth College, Hanover, NH

Corresponding author:

Joshua J. Levy, PhD
Department of Dermatology
Department of Epidemiology
Dartmouth Hitchcock Medical Center
Geisel School of Medicine
1 Medical Center Drive, Lebanon, NH 03756
Email: joshua.j.levy@dartmouth.edu

Funding sources: JL is supported by NIH grants R24GM141194, P20GM104416 and P20GM130454

Conflicts of Interest: None declared.

Patient Consent on File: Not applicable

Reprint requests: Joshua Levy

Manuscript word count: *** words

References: ***

Figures and tables: *** [maximum 8 total]

Supplementary figures: 0

Supplementary tables: 0

Attachments: ***

Abstract (345/350):

Objective: Recent advances in sophisticated computer vision techniques have accelerated the development of methods for interpreting dermatological images. While a plethora of studies

have been published in the last few years, the sheer volume of published work has made it challenging to determine which approaches are state-of-the-art, and what sorts of potential limitations warrant further study. Deep learning algorithms developed for the HAM10000 dataset, a large dataset of dermoscopic images, exemplifies the burgeoning development and research of artificial intelligence (AI) applications adapted for dermatological imaging, where papers are published every other week. This systematic review aims to provide a comprehensive survey of deep learning models trained and tested on the HAM10000 dataset, paying special attention to their innovations and limitations, alongside broader qualitative perspectives concerning the direction of progress and challenges for research utilizing this dataset. In so doing, readers will gain a deeper appreciation for current HAM10000 benchmarks, as well as context for future findings.

Methods: We conducted an exhaustive query of MEDLINE and PubMed Central (PMC) databases through PubMed using keywords including 'HAM10000', 'HAM-10000', and "HAM 10000". Studies published between 2018 (the year of inception for the dataset) and 2022 were included.

Results: A total of 31 studies met inclusion criteria for this review, with each study falling in to at least one of six categories: feasibility, classification, segmentation, distributed computation, and validation. Across all categories, model accuracy ranged from 0.84 to 0.99. The most common model used in the literature is CNNs, with DenseNet, in particular, being especially common. The most common reason for exclusion of a study was biased analysis with overlap of training/testing sets.

Conclusions: 1) attention matters as well as manually segmenting areas of interest prior to classification, 2) transfer learning often provide additional performance gains versus model architecture changes, and there are several 3) validation and 4) user-centered design challenges which must be addressed prior to widespread implementation. Taken together, balancing clinical intuition with technical quantitative expertise and addressing these challenges can lead to the development of more accurate and clinically useful deep learning models for dermatological images.

Graphical Abstract:

Keywords: dermoscopic images; deep learning; general dermatology; machine learning, medical dermatology; cutaneous oncology

Statement of Significance: (88/100)

Problem or Issue	With an increasing number of publications and ever changing approaches to analyzing dermatologic images, it is difficult to identify and track the promise and significance of emerging approaches in the field
What is known?	HAM10000 dataset consists of 10,015 high-quality dermoscopic images and serves as an optimal dataset for advancing the field of dermatologic computer vision
What this paper adds	A focused and in-depth review of deep learning models trained and tested on the HAM10000 dataset to underscore recent advancements and challenges in this field

Abbreviations:

Artificial intelligence (AI); State-of-the-art (SOTA); Sensitivity (SE); Dice (Dice score); Acc (Accuracy); Average symmetric surface distance (ASSD); Specificity (SP), Artificial neural network (ANN); Confidence interval (CI); Grouping of multi-scale attention blocks (GMAB); Area-under-curve (AUC); Precision (PR); Recall (RE); F1-score (F1); Generative adversarial

network (GAN); Splitfed learning (SFL); Multihead splitfed learning (MHSFL); Internet of Medical Things (IoMT); Transfer learning (TL); Internet of things (IoT); Convolutional neural network (CNN); Extreme learning machine (ELM); Gradient-weighted class activation mapping (Grad-CAM); Jaccard index (JI); Fully connected (FC); Long short-term memory (LSTM); Automated machine learning (AutoML); Variational autoencoder (VAE); Neural architecture search (NAS); Hybrid whale optimization (HWO); Moth flame optimization (MFO); High dimension contrast technique (HDCT); Decision tree (DT); Naïve bayes (NB); Multilayer preceptor (MLP); Support vector machine (SVM); Structural similarity index (SSIM); Conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN); Diverse data augmentation generative adversarial network (DDA-GAN); Machine learning (ML).

Introduction:

Computer vision has long been an area of intense focus for artificial intelligence (AI) research. In the past decade, advancements in hardware and model architecture have raised the performance of these models to new heights. In dermatology specifically, computer vision methods are uniquely poised to alleviate clinician caseload burden through autonomous triaging, diagnosis assistance, and telehealth synergy. As such, a growing number of datasets containing dermatological images have emerged in recent years. Published in 2018, the HAM10000 dataset consists of 10,015 high-quality dermoscopic images spanning seven distinct diagnostic categories: melanoma, melanocytic nevus, basal cell carcinoma, actinic keratosis, benign keratosis, dermatofibroma and vascular lesion. Dermoscopic images provide a more granular level of detail for diagnostic purposes, and provide much more controlled, consistent images when compared to clinical images alone. This collection of images has allowed researchers to make substantial progress in dermatological computer vision. What sets this dataset apart from other large-scale skin datasets (e.g., ISIC 2017, BCN20000) is its diverse disease representation (representing seven distinct classes – e.g., melanoma, melanocytic nevus, basal cell carcinoma, etc.– compared to just benign/malignant for common binary classification datasets, extensive inclusion of patient characteristics, including age, sex, lesion location, and methods of diagnostic confirmation of algorithmic findings).

The HAM10000 dataset has bolstered the advancement of several different dermatological computer vision tasks. Common computer vision tasks in this context include classification (e.g., diagnosing a skin lesion as benign/malignant), segmentation (e.g., localization of lesions), and synthetic image generation (which can be hugely important for a range of tasks, including rapid production of immunochemistry stains and teaching images). In the classification task, deep neural networks are frequently trained to predict, given a dermoscopic image, either one among two classes (binary classification) or several classes (multi-class classification). For example, models trained using the HAM10000 dataset can predict whether a lesion is malignant or benign, or provide a specific diagnosis/prognosis (grade/stage). In segmentation tasks, deep neural networks are trained to identify and localize specific image features. In lesion segmentation, for example, the objective is to delineate, in a pixel-wise manner, diseased from healthy skin tissue. Further, considerable focus in computer vision research has

recently shifted toward synthetic image generation. These approaches can generate photorealistic images, frequently to supplement the amount and diversity of training data available as means to improve classification task performance.

The expanding scope and reach of dermatological computer vision applications have revealed opportunities to extract valuable insights from dermatoscopic images and non-trivial limitations and challenges that may preclude the wide-spread adoption of these technologies. With so many papers being published in this space, it is difficult for researchers to identify the promise and significance of most approaches. This plurality of information could lead to publication reporting bias—authors unfamiliar with the current state-of-the-art approaches may be more likely to report out-of-date performance statistics, artificially deflating current benchmarks, and thereby misrepresenting their contributions. In some cases, research published with biased evaluation methodologies may inflate their performance statistics and set unrealistic performance expectations, potentially leading to the adoption of suboptimal techniques. This, in turn, can discourage the publication of more realistic yet fairly evaluated results, hindering further progress.

While a larger undertaking might seek to review publications concerning dermatological computer vision more broadly – or indeed dermatological uses of AI – this study conducts a focused and in-depth examination of a popular example of dermatological application to underscore recent challenges in this field. We comprehensively review all studies involving the HAM10000 dataset since its initial publication, their outcomes, and potential sources of limitation/bias. In so doing, this work summarizes the research fostered by the HAM10000 dataset and delineates state-of-the-art results in their respective categories. Finally, we discuss the strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of this body of literature, and areas for further research. The contributions of this work may be summarized as follows:

1. Review and summarize research based on the HAM10000 dataset, highlighting the range of approaches, modeling architectures, and methods used across the literature.
2. Report state-of-the-art benchmarks across the various research categories (e.g., classification, segmentation, generation).
3. Evaluate this growing body of literature, paying special attention to limitations that further research should be cautious to avoid.

Methods:

We conducted an exhaustive query of MEDLINE and PubMed Central (PMC) databases through PubMed using keywords including ‘HAM10000’, ‘HAM-10000’, and “HAM 10000”. Studies published between 2018 (the year of inception for the dataset) and 2022 were included.

Studies were first screened based on their perceived relevance to AI and computer vision as surmised within study abstracts. Then, studies were assessed for eligibility and excluded based on the following criteria:

1. Systematic reviews/meta-analyses.
2. Failure to include machine learning/deep learning.
3. Failure to both train and test models on the HAM10000 dataset.
4. Flawed or deceptive training/testing methodologies, including:
 - a. image overlap between the training/testing sets.
 - b. duplicate images in the test set.

Exclusion criteria 1 and 2 were used to select studies that leveraged the HAM10000 dataset for machine learning and deep learning. In contrast, criteria 3 and 4 were adopted to enable a fair and standard comparison of model performances. If models were trained on the HAM10000 dataset and tested on other datasets, subsequent model comparison would become difficult. Similarly, when studies produce training/testing cohorts with image overlap, or testing cohorts with duplicate images, the results become less robust, and comparison between studies becomes problematic.

This process of screening is further illustrated in **Figure 1**. After screening, studies were grouped into categories based on study purpose. Studies that pursued multiple topics were categorized based on the focus of their work.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of inclusion criteria. Using the keywords “HAM10000,” “HAM-10000,” and “HAM 10000,” 52 studies were retrieved from MEDLINE and PubMed Central. Of these, 21 studies were excluded: 17 due to topic irrelevance during the abstract screening process, and 4 due to inappropriate methodology (mainly exclusion criteria 4). The remaining 31 studies were included in qualitative analysis.

Afterwards, studies were distinguished into one of six categories: feasibility, classification, image synthesis, segmentation, distributed computation, and validation. Feasibility studies attempted to assess the barriers to implementing deep learning algorithms in pre-existing clinical workflows by non-experts. Classification studies, whether binary or multi-class, leveraged computer vision models to classify skin lesions across various categories and tasks. Image synthesis studies attempted to generate synthetic skin data. Segmentation studies focused on identifying target regions within an image (e.g., skin disease, hair follicles, etc...). Distributed computation studies sought to train and test computer vision models in a decentralized manner, such that no one system had access to all patient data, and model

training was distributed across computational arrangements. Finally, validation studies attempted to measure the performance of SOTA models in non-ideal conditions, such as when exposed to novel diseases, or when images were captured in sub-standard lighting.

Results:

In total, 31 studies were included in the final review. These studies are summarized in **Table 1**, which details the results of these studies, including their methods, performance statistics, and potential limitations. Studies were grouped into six categories (**Figure 2A**). The number of publications/citations per year was also assessed. (**Figure 2B** and **Figure 2C**).

Figure 2: Characteristics, model accuracy, and model type of included studies. (A) The 31 included studies were grouped into six categories: feasibility (n=1), classification (multi-class: n=17; binary: n=1), image synthesis (n=1), segmentation (lesion segmentation: n=1; artifact detection: n=2), distributed computation (n=3), and validation (n=2). (B) Most studies (n=15) were published in 2022, followed by 2021 (n=7), 2020 (n=5), 2019 (n=2), and 2018 (n=1, the year of inception for the HAM10000 dataset). (C) The HAM10000 inception paper published in 2018 has been cited 1496 times from 2018-2022, followed by 215 citations from 2019-2022 for those published in 2019, 44 citations from 2020-2022 for those published in 2020, 441 citations from 2021-2022 for those published in 2021, and 108 citations in 2022 for those published in 2022.

Figure 3: Model Accuracy of Included Studies. Color-coded by category: feasibility (black), artifact detection (purple), validation (green), classification (light blue), segmentation (red), and distributed computation (dark blue). Note that the first deep learning studies were only published in 2019, while the original dataset was published in 2018.

Since the inception of the dataset in 2018, performance across all studied categories has increased considerably, though this trend has not been monotonic (**Figure 3**). Four studies were excluded during the eligibility evaluation stage due to biased training and evaluation methodologies, corresponding to exclusion criteria 4A and 4B (**Supplementary Materials: Excluded Studies**).

Authors	Study Category	Model Performance	Limitations/Comments
<i>Karri et al., 2022 [1].</i>	Image Segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SE: 0.960 • Dice: 0.918 • Acc: 0.973 • ASSD: 0.15 	Karri et al. utilized multi-module semantic guided attention to improve lesion segmentation. One substantial merit of this approach is that it increases model explainability, via attention heatmaps.
Samsudin et al., 2022 [2].	Multi-class Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.989 • SE: 0.965 • SP: 0.994 	Samsudin et al. combine multi-resolution empirical mode decomposition and local binary pattering to produce image texture embeddings invariant to uneven illumination and rotation. A simple ANN processed these embeddings. One significant limitation of this work is that only 490 training images and 315 test images are used. It is difficult to know whether performance will generalize.
Reis et al., 2022 [3].	Binary Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 94.59 (CI: 86.73–98.51) • SE: 97.50 (CI: 86.84–99.94) • SP: 91.18 (CI: 76.32–98.14) 	Reis et al. couple U-Net image segmentation with their novel InSiNet classifier. One significant limitation of this work is that 1323 samples were used in the training dataset, while only 74 were used for validation and testing datasets.
<i>Qian et al., 2022 [4].</i>	Multi-class Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SE: 0.735 • SP: 0.964 • Acc: 0.916 • AUC: 0.971 	The main innovation in Qian et al. is the grouping of multi-scale attention blocks (GMAB), which allow the classification model to focus more on the diseased lesion. They also utilize class-specific loss weighting to combat data imbalance.
<i>Katsch et al., 2022 [5].</i>	Validation Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification AUC w/o artifacts: 0.8 • Segmentation AUC w/o artifacts: 0.72 (Faster R-CNN) • Classification AUC w/ artifacts: 0.77 • Segmentation AUC w/ artifacts: 0.67 (Faster R-CNN) 	Katsch et al. studied the impact of common image artifacts on image classification and segmentation tasks, concluding that these artifacts greatly decrease model performance.
<i>Xin et al., 2022 [6].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.943 • PR: 0.941 • AUC: 0.987 	The major innovation of Xin et al. is the multi-scale and overlapping sliding windows approach to patch embeddings, and the label shuffling to combat dataset imbalance. One limitation of this work is that class specific AUCs are not formally reported in the text.

<i>Li et al., 2022 [7].</i>	Multi-class classification/Synthetic Augmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.958 • PR: 0.961 • RE: 0.958 • F1: 0.957 	Li et al. propose the use of GANs and ensembling via feature fusion. Additionally, they propose a novel form of spatial attention that incorporates novel dilated pyramid pooling intended to extract multiscale features.
<i>Joshi et al., 2022 [8].</i>	Distributed Computation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.872 • PR: 0.8672 • RE: 0.872 • F1: 0.866 • AUC: 0.975 	Joshi et al. examine splitfed learning (SFL) and multihead splitfed learning (MHSL). They conclude that SFL is superior to MHSL on healthcare datasets, though they do not explain the mechanism behind this difference.
<i>Islam et al., 2022 [9].</i>	Distributed Computation/ Data Privacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.867 	Islam et al. implement a IoMT-based computer-assisted diagnosis system using a range of TL models in conjunction with a IoT-based data collection system. One limitation is that they do not report class specific metrics.
<i>Popescu et al., 2022 [10].</i>	Multi-class Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.8671 	Popescu et al. developed a collective intelligence system (i.e., model ensemble) fusing 9 individual CNNs. The ensemble model learned adaptive weights for each model and achieved substantially higher accuracy than any individual model. The ensemble model, however, took nearly 10x as long to inference as the fastest individual model.
<i>Aladhadh et al., 2022* [11].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PR: 0.960 • RE: 0.965 • F1: 0.97 • Acc: 0.961 	Aladhadh et al. explored using a vision transformer on the HAM10000 dataset, showing SOTA results. One significant limitation of this study is that the authors did not precisely clarify their augmentation protocol. Therefore, it is possible – though not certain – that they engaged in data augmentation where augmentations of training set images were seen in the test set.
<i>Bardou et al., 2022 [12].</i>	Artifact Detection/Removal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.934 • PR: 0.931 	Bardou et al. developed a variational autoencoder to generate hair free images. Because generated images were low quality, they utilized structural similarity index (a form of perceptual loss). However, they note that underlying pixels can still be erroneously altered in this process.
<i>Afza et al., 2022 [13].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.930 • SE: 0.835 • SP: 0.932 • AUC: 0.978 	Afza et al. designed a range of computationally efficient methods for image classification, notably hybrid whale optimization and entropy-mutual information for feature fusion. Backpropagation based fully

			connected layers are also replaced by an extreme learning machine (ELM).
<i>Wang et al., 2022 [14].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.906 	Wang et al. developed a multimodal CNN that integrates patient metadata alongside visual input. Notably, they also provide a range of features for model explainability, including shapely analysis and Grad-CAM. One limitation is that the authors do not seem to report class specific performance metrics.
<i>Mohanty et al., 2022 [15].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.941 	Mohanty et al. explored a range of distinct feature fusion strategies. They used an ensemble of three distinct models, in conjunction with optimized feature fusion strategies such as the artificial jellyfish algorithm, to produce optimal embeddings. One limitation of this study is that class specific performance metrics were not reported.
<i>Lama et al., 2022 [16].</i>	Artifact Detection/Removal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.982 • JI: 0.65 	Lama et al. developed and deployed a novel UNet solution for segmenting hair and ruler marks in clinical images, which deploys EfficientNet as the encoder, and squeeze-and-excitation residual structures in the decoder. A limitation they note is the sheer effort required to obtain high quality mask annotations for train/test/validation cohorts.
<i>Combalia et al., 2022 [17]</i>	Validation Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 82.0% balanced accuracy on HAM10000 	Combalia et al. performed a wide-scale validation study that examined the performance of 129 SOTA image classification algorithms. One limitation in this study is that the authors report primarily balanced accuracy, one among a range of distinct performance measures of interest (e.g., AUC-ROC, precision, recall).
<i>Thomas, 2021 [18].</i>	Multi-class classification	N/A	Thomas et al. compared Alexnet, DenseNet, ResNet50, InceptionResNetv2, VGG and GoogleNet trained on image data against those same models trained on image data and corresponding image metadata. One limitation of this study is that while performance differences between conditions are reported, the absolute performances are not made clear.

Jain et al.,
2021 [19].

Multi-class classification

- Acc: 0.905
- RE: 0.896
- PR: 0.888
- F1: 0.890

Jain et al. compare six different transfer learning networks – VGG19, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, ResNet50, Xception, and MobileNet – for image classification. They find that Xception performs best. One limitation in this study is that though confusion matrices and percent incorrect statistics were reported, there were no tables for class specific metrics, making it difficult to understand broader performance trends.

Havei et al.,
2021 [20].

GAN/Synthetic Image
Generation

- Acc: 0.578-0.656
- FID: 1.224-4.893
- IS: 1.300-1.449

Havei et al. further existing work in synthetic image generation by proposing a dual adversarial inference framework with augmented disentanglement constraints. Using this framework, they can disentangle image content from image style. One important consequence of this work is that it can allow for the generation of hybrid images by mixing the style and content from multiple sources.

Khan et al.,
2021 [21]

Multi-class classification

- Acc: 90.67
- SE: 90.20
- FNR: 9.33

Khan et al. combined custom lesion segmentation CNNs with high dimension contrast transform based saliency segmentation to improve segmentation performance. Then, TL was used to train a DenseNet-201 model with these segmented models. Finally, extracted features from the FC layers of DenseNet are down sampled, combined using the multi canonical correlation approach, and passed to a multi-class extreme learning machine classifier. One limitation of this study is that it does not report class specific performance metrics.

Khan et al.,
2021 [22].

Multi-class classification

- Acc: 0.884

In this work, Khan et al. produced highly discriminant image embeddings through a combination of deep saliency segmentation, which segmented the image, transfer learning classification, moth flame optimization on the resultant feature embeddings from the classifier, and multiset maximum correlation analysis to combine embeddings. Finally, the resultant features are classified using kernel extreme learning machine. One limitation of this study is that the authors do not

			include class specific performances for the segmentation CNN, so it is unclear how the model performs on highly scare samples.
<i>Srinivasu et al., 2021 [23].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.853 	Srinivasu et al. designed a novel combination of MobileNet V2 and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to be implemented on a mobile device. Though not the focus of this study, their proposed mobile application architecture is not evaluated in real world scenarios, so conclusions about the efficacy of this mobile system should be drawn with caution.
<i>Huang et al., 2021 [24].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.858 	Huang et al. devised a lightweight CNN based on EfficientNet for the purposes of deployment on cloud platforms and mobile devices and achieved SOTA results.
<i>Ameri, 2020 [25].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AUC: 0.91 • Acc: 0.84 • SE: 0.81 • SP: 0.88 	Ameri leveraged a TL based AlexNet model for image classification. Some limitations of this study include the more limited training and testing cohorts (n = 3060 and 340, respectively). Additionally, vascular lesions were excluded from the predicted classes.
<i>Hansen et al., 2020 [26].</i>	Multi-class Classification/ Semi-supervised classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.77 • AUC: 0.755 	Hansel et al. leverage MixMatch and Nullspace Tuning methods to increase the performance of image classification models in low labeled resource settings. Using only 40% of the HAM10000 dataset, they are able to achieve SOTA results comparable with methods trained on the entire dataset. The authors do not report class specific performance metrics.
<i>Allyn et al., 2020 [27].</i>	Multi-class classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.84 (unperturbed images) • Acc: 0.67 (perturbed images) 	Allyn et al. evaluated the effect of undetectable image perturbations on the classification performance of the DenseNet-201 model. The trained adversarial neural network created undetectable perturbations – as classified by external observers – and substantially lowered the performance of the classification model.
<i>Wang et al., 2020 [28].</i>	Binary classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acc: 0.925 • AUC: 0.887 	Wang et al. developed a shallow CNN to distinguish actinic keratosis from benign keratosis. They showed that their method outperformed a range of conventional models, including AlexNet, GoogLeNet, and ResNet.

<i>Faes et al., 2019 [29].</i>	Feasibility Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AUC: 0.93 (automated network) 	Faes et al. examined whether non-expert healthcare workers could devise high performing machine learning algorithms using a neural architecture search framework hosted on Google Cloud AutoML. Results indicate that non-experts can produce high performing models on simple datasets, with more limited success on complex datasets.
<i>Mobiny et al., 2019 [30].</i>	Multi-class classification/ Model interpretability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DenseNet-169 Acc: 0.814 Bayesian DenseNet-169 Acc: 0.836. Hybrid machine-physician Acc: 0.90. 	Mobiny et al. demonstrated that Bayesian deep networks can substantially improve the performance of conventional models while providing a confidence estimate. Hybrid machine-physician performance far exceeds model performance.
<i>Tschandl et al., 2018 [31].</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N/A 	HAM10000 dataset is introduced here.

Table 1: Summary of included studies including study type, model performance, and limitations/comments.

Studies are listed in order of recency. Different studies had different performance metrics. AUC = area under curve; Acc = accuracy; SE = sensitivity; SP = specificity; F1 = F1-score; FNR = false negative rate; FPR = false positive rate; PR = precision; RE = recall; ASSD = average symmetric surface distance; JI = Jaccard index; FID = Frechet inception distance; IS = Inception score. **Additional clarity is needed on the methods of these studies.*

Discussion:

Classification:

As shown in **Figure 2A**, image classification tasks represented the majority of studies published. All but two of these studies (n=19) predicted one of several potential diagnoses (i.e., multi-class), while the remaining studies predicted whether an image is malignant or benign (i.e., binary). The classification methods surveyed relied on either single deep learning models or ensemble methods, confirming results in Jeong et al. [32]. Importantly, these studies demonstrated substantial variation in methodology, especially in: 1) pre-processing – i.e., image processing before classification, such as color normalization or contrast enhancement – and 2) feature extraction – i.e., the process through which the most salient portions of an image are crystallized and provided to the model, like dimensionality reduction – as well as in 3) model architectural choice (i.e., CNN vs Vision Transformer). It is worth emphasizing that these methodological decisions greatly impact downstream model performance, particularly on class-specific performances, shown in **Table 2**.

Data Preprocessing and Augmentation: Studies utilized various image processing augmentation techniques such as contrast stretching, horizontal/vertical flips and rotations, image cutouts, and oversampling (**Supplementary Table 2**). Image augmentation techniques

can be largely separated into two categories: standard image augmentation and neural image augmentation. Here, standard augmentation refers to those non-neural, statistical transformations that can be applied to images to prevent overfitting and increase model generalizability. Standard image augmentation techniques include random horizontal/vertical flipping, rotation, color jitter, contrast, cutout, and oversampling. For example, Qian et al. utilized horizontal/vertical flip, random rotation, cutout, and oversampling to increase sample counts from the minority classes [4]. Neural image augmentation, on the other hand, refers to those techniques that leverage generative methods, such as generative adversarial networks (GAN), to synthesize additional images to supplement the existing training corpus, or variational autoencoders (VAE), to denoise data. For instance, Li et al. use GANs to expand a dermoscopy dataset [7]. Both forms of augmentation were used to combat dataset class imbalance, though standard augmentation was far more common (**Figure 4**). Image augmentation – in both its standard and neural forms – has substantially increased model performance in the downstream prediction task. For researchers working with the HAM10000 dataset, class imbalance remains a prominent issue, and, therefore, augmentation techniques that seek to expand the available dataset (e.g., GAN) or increase the number of samples from minority classes (e.g., oversampling or GAN) should play a prominent role in augmentation schemes.

Additionally, some studies utilized lesion segmentation as part of their preprocessing. For example, Khan et al. trained a 16-layer CNN to localize lesions, before utilizing a DenseNet201/ResNet101 transfer learning module for the classification task [22]. This method assumes that only the relevant part of the image (i.e., the diseased skin) is needed for downstream prediction. While this approach appears to have numerous advantages, Khan et al. did not measure the specific benefit associated with this pre-processing in their paper. However, they did note that their overall approach beat SOTA approaches by nearly 7% in accuracy and sensitivity, achieving accuracy and sensitivity of 0.91 and 0.90, respectively (compared to 0.83 for SOTA accuracy and sensitivity). Future research may examine the merits of lesion segmentation as part of the preprocessing workflow.

Figure 4: Distribution of Augmentation and Balancing Practices in Multiclass Classification Studies. Data augmentation and balancing were observed throughout classification studies. In total, 19 classification studies were examined. 13 of the examined studies (68%) utilized some form of standard augmentation, whereas only 1 leveraged GANs for neural augmentation.

Feature Extraction Approaches: Previous classification studies employed widely different feature extraction approaches. In an attempt to generate feature maps sensitive to both spatial information (i.e., which regions of the image are substantial) and channel information (i.e., which image channel contains the most salient information), Li et al. concatenated spatial and channel attention feature maps [7]. Using vision transformers, Xin et al. generated multi-scale patch embeddings – which can dynamically assign greater weight to tissue contexts at different scales [6]. This approach allowed models to incorporate information of varying depth and focus. Afza et al. used a version of autoML – NASNET large – as a feature extractor, before combining a hybrid whale optimization (HWO) algorithm with fuzzy entropy mutual information, to select the most important portions of the feature embedding [13]. The authors could then fuse these distinct feature vectors (one from HWO, and one from fuzzy entropy mutual information) using optimal feature fusion, which removes feature redundancies, before using an extreme learning model for the final classification.

Similarly, after feature extraction using TL models, Khan et al. leveraged a moth flame optimization (MFO) algorithm to pick out the most important features of the original embedding, thereby retaining the most essential information while shrinking the dimensionality of the embedding before the final fully-connected layers [22]. In other work, Khan et al., leveraged a deep high dimension contrast transform (HDCT) based saliency segmentation

approach to their feature extraction, after which they pursued a maximum mutual information approach for feature fusion [21]. HDCT generates lesion masks by computing a saliency map using deep learning features. This, coupled with another image mask generated through a different segmentation algorithm, allowed Khan et al. to generate high-quality lesion masks relatively efficiently (i.e., without using much deeper networks).

While many feature extraction approaches exist, best performing methods apply attention-based approaches at different image scales to capture the most salient information at different levels of granularity. In general, neural approaches seem to be the most promising (i.e., multi-scale patch embeddings), however, a range of neural architecture search methods have shown high efficacy as well (e.g., MFO and HWO).

Model Architectures: Authors leveraged several different model architectures, from simple hand-crafted CNNs (i.e., small number of convolutional layers), to EfficientNet, to combinations of inception, ResNet, and DenseNet architectures, to Vision Transformers (**Supplementary Table 1**). These architectures, and their permutations, have been widely utilized across computer vision tasks due to their performance, customizability, and generalizability [10], [33]–[35]. Indeed, though some computer vision architectures are applied broadly across many different tasks, some architectures lend themselves better to certain tasks than others. Several novel architectures have been proposed to bolster dermatological image classification. Srinivasu et al. combined MobileNetV2 with LSTM, reaching an overall testing accuracy of 0.853 [23]. Their architecture reduced classification inference times and total computation two-fold over the original MobileNet model. The authors demonstrated that their model could run efficiently on a smartphone and deployed in the clinical setting. Others, like Mobiny et al., combined Bayesian deep networks with the standard DenseNet-169, increasing overall model performance and improving accuracy by .02, from 0.814 to 0.836 [30]. By employing Bayesian methods to sample a predictive posterior distribution from a posterior distribution of weights and biases, models were configured to report a credible interval for their class predictions. Reporting diagnostic uncertainty through Bayesian modeling approaches may present information on reliability of the study findings which can be factored into clinical decision making. These principles were tested in spirit through a study which simulated a hybrid, semi-autonomous clinician–machine learning workflow, where predictions with sufficiently high confidence were not referred to clinicians. Models employed in this setting reached a classification accuracy of 0.90, while only 35% of the cases were ultimately referred to clinicians [30].

Additionally, some authors have proposed more standard machine learning techniques for final classification. For instance, Afza et al. utilize an extreme learning machine (ELM) to produce final diagnoses [13]. These models tend to generalize better than their deep-learning counterparts while learning thousands of times faster than networks trained using backpropagation. Many promising innovations have also incorporated attention, along channel and spatial dimensions. For instance, Li et al. integrate both channel and spatial attention, alongside attention distribution techniques like dilation – which allows a model to see an image

at different scales (i.e., zoom) – to markedly improve model performance, by, at least in part, orienting the model towards more relevant image features, like arborizing vessels in basal cell carcinoma or blue-white veil and atypical pigment network in melanoma [7], [36]. Isolating these features has increased diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity in making diagnoses based on dermoscopic images alone [36], [37]. The analysis, in the article by Li et al., showed that models incorporating both channel and spatial attention captured key semantic regions of the disease in ways that models without these attention modules failed to capture [7]. Qian et al. also incorporated grouped multi-scale attention blocks (GMAB) to capture multi-scale fine-grained features, thereby improving the model's ability to focus on diseased areas, and recognize class-specific features [4]. These GMABs differentially weighed low-level feature information (e.g., edge and texture) and high-level features (e.g., shapes and textures). In so doing, they achieved accuracy and AUC of 0.916 and 0.971, respectively [4].

While many architectures have been proposed for image classification, the best performing ones in this setting employed attention mechanisms. Future research should seek to expand the use of attention mechanisms and transformer architectures for classification on the HAM10000 dataset. Furthermore, work needs to be done to increase model transparency in line with Mobiny et al., where model confidence was quantified [30]. This will, ultimately, increase the usefulness of these models in the clinical setting.

Transfer Learning versus Novel Model Architectures: Many studies also relied on TL to improve model performance. TL leverages knowledge gained in one domain and applies this information to a different – but related – domain. This involves using weights and biases from a previous, related training iteration to initialize the parameters for another model trained on information with additional relevance. Jain et al., for example, compared the performance of VGG19, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, ResNet50, Xception, DenseNet, and MobileNet models utilizing transfer learning from the ImageNet dataset onto the HAM10000 dataset [19], [38]. The ImageNet dataset contains over 14 million annotated images from over 21 thousand diverse classes such as animals, clothing, and vehicles. Here, the authors demonstrated the effectiveness of TL from Imagenet to the HAM10000 dataset. Importantly, the study authors also demonstrated how distinct models may respond differently to TL, and how these gains in performance are contingent on consequent training regimens. For example, they showed that VGG19, InceptionV3, and ResNet50, showed a decline in accuracy while using a training protocol that had duplicate images (0.67 to 0.66, 0.82 to 0.79, and 0.81 to 0.77, respectively), while InceptionResNetV2, MobileNet, and Xception, showed an increase in accuracy (0.81 to 0.85, 0.82 to 0.88, and 0.81 to 0.90, respectively) under this same paradigm [19]. Khan et al. utilized transfer-learned models as feature encoders for alternate classification techniques, like ELMs, where transfer learning remains extremely useful as a source of informational transfer between domains [22]. Other studies, particularly those proposing novel architectures or leveraging new techniques, did not leverage transfer learning. For example, Xin et al. proposed a novel vision transformer for dermoscopic image classification and trained this model without access to pre-existing weights and biases to leverage [6]. Similarly, Aladhadh et al. did not mention transfer learning in their training of a medical vision transformer, implying that they

trained this model from scratch – that is, with randomly initialized starting parameters [11]. Despite training in this fashion, Aladhadh et al. achieved results that beat SOTA (F1-score and accuracy were 0.97, 0.96, respectively)[11].

Therefore, transfer learning is imperative for researchers using architectures for which pre-trained weights are available. Though, as Jain et al. show, some underlying architectures exhibit greater increases in performance via TL than others, and researchers must be cognizant of these facts when selecting model architectures [19]. To facilitate transfer learning, researchers producing novel architectures may consider publishing their model to expand access to TL.

Study	Metric	Year	AKIEC	BCC	DF	MEL	NV	VASC	BKL	Overall	Model Architecture
Li et al., [7].	Acc	2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.96	Fuzzy rank-based ensemble of multilayer feature fusion convolutional neural network (CNN) models
Samsudin et al., [2].	Acc	2022	0.93	0.95	0.98	1	0.95	1	0.93	0.99	ANN
Qian et al., [4].	AUC	2022	0.958	0.98	0.97	0.935	0.98	0.998	0.958	0.916	Novel CNN model with grouping of multi-scale attention mechanism and class-specific loss weighting
Xin et al., [6].	Acc	2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.943	Vision Transformer
Popescu et al., [10].	Acc	2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.867	Ensemble with CNNs
Aladhadh et al., [11].	Acc	2022	0.96	0.91	1	0.95	0.97	1	0.94	0.96	Medical Vision Transformer
Afza et al., [13].	Acc	2022	0.95	0.97	0.90	0.92	0.96	0.91	0.91	0.93	Extreme Learning Machine (ELM)
Wang et al., [14].	Acc	2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.906	Interpretability-Based Multimodal Convolutional Neural Network (IM-CNN). EfficientNet base.

Mohanty and Pradhan et al., [15].	Acc	2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.941	Decision Tree (DT), Naïve Bayesian (NB), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Support Vector Machine (SVM)
Thomas [18].	Acc	2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Various pre-trained CNNs (ResNet, AlexNet, etc.
Jain et al., [19].	Prec	2021	0.92	0.88	0.71	0.58	0.94	1	0.68	0.905	Various pre-trained CNNs (VGG19, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, ResNet50, Xception, and MobileNet)
Khan et al., [22].	Acc	2021	0.904	0.94	0.84	0.906	0.88	0.895	0.930	0.907	Kernel Extreme Learning Machine (KELM)
Khan et al., [21].	Acc	2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.884	CNN + ELM
Srinivasu et al., [23].	Acc	2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.8534	MobileNet-based LSTM
Huang et al., [24].	Acc	2021	0.981	0.97	0.99	0.93	0.91	0.993	0.939	0.858	EfficientNet
Ameri [25].	Acc	2020	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.84	AlexNet
Hansen et al., [26].	Acc	2020	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	~0.83*	DenseNet
Allyn et al., [27].	Acc	2020	0.7	0.72	0.9	0.66	0.91	0.91	0.67	0.84	DenseNet-201
Mobiny et al., [30].	Acc	2019	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.90-0.95**	Bayesian VGG-16, ResNet-50, and DenseNet-169

Table 2: Multiclass Classification Performance by Class. 19 multiclass classification studies are analyzed for class specific performance. 8 studies provided class specific performance metrics. All but one study reported absolute performance metrics for overall classifier performance. **Hansen et al. reported balanced multiclass accuracy improvements, rather than single overall accuracy; this value is estimated.* *** This is the overall accuracy Mobiny et al., achieve through the hybrid clinician-machine workflow.*

Segmentation:

Image segmentation tasks are another major area of focus in computer vision, aiming to elucidate regions of interest within an image. The HAM10000 has been instrumental in this domain, allowing for the investigation of various questions in image segmentation. These studies can be distinguished into two groups: lesion segmentation and artifact detection. The former offers tremendous clinical utility by emphasizing to the clinician the relevant, though sometimes subtle, dermoscopic features that differentiate benign and malignant lesions. Recent advancements have produced models with more consistent results to take advantage of the significant impact of automatic segmentation in the early diagnosis and detection of skin cancer [39]. Successful artifact detection (and removal), on the other hand, is of major significance to other tasks in computer vision, where image artifacts can decrease model performance (e.g., image artifacts worsen image classification models). Many of the same considerations that were salient in the case of image classification models remain relevant here: selection of model architecture, training routine, and loss function are critical for model performance.

Lesion segmentation: The HAM10000 dataset has been commonly used for lesion localization, as each image in the dataset is provided a corresponding mask created by experts, which distinguishes diseased from healthy skin in a pixel-wise manner. Recent advancements include work published by Karri et al., who developed a lesion segmentation model that utilized semantic-guided attention to increase model explainability, or the ability to understand the reasons underlying a model's decision [1]. Citing the limited clinical utility of these segmentation models due to their low explainability, they drew extensively on channel and spatial attention, coupled with gradient visualizations, to show clinicians where model attention persisted during segmentation decisions. Overall, the proposed model achieved a Dice score of 91.75, a sensitivity of 96.03, and an accuracy of 97.29, outperforming a standard UNet by 11.59% for Dice score, 5.97% for sensitivity, and 5.97% for accuracy. These findings suggest the importance of both spatial and channel attention in medical image segmentation tasks to improve performance and enhance model explainability.

Artifact detection and removal: Another area of focus within the segmentation problem has been noise and artifact detection, which has several implications for image classification algorithms. These classification algorithms tend to perform substantially better on high-fidelity, denoised data. Therefore, noise and artifact detection algorithms can significantly improve dataset quality by detecting and correcting image noise and artifact patterns. For example, Bardou et al. use VAEs to detect and remove hair from HAM10000 images. Their approach involves using an encoder, which learns to ignore hair as it builds a latent distribution for the underlying dataset, and a decoder, which produces the hair-free image [12]. This approach compared favorably with many other state-of-the-art approaches (e.g., successfully eliminating all types of hair, not requiring paired images, having a simpler architecture with fewer layers, less complex loss function). However, they note that their approach, though successful in removing hair from images, frequently compromised image quality, representing a substantial drawback for approaches of this kind. To ameliorate deficits in image quality, Bardou et al. incorporated perceptual loss – a loss aimed at tracking the visual quality of a generated image

by comparing image representations at deeper neural network layers to penalize more complex imaging features – into the total loss of their VAE, which they found substantially improves the quality of generated images (structural similarity index [SSIM] = 0.805 for SSIM + L2 versus just 0.770 for SSIM alone).

In a similar domain, Lama et al. developed a ChimeraNet architecture with a pre-trained EfficientNet, to detect and segment hair and ruler mark structures in dermoscopic images. Their approach was motivated by the observation that hair and ruler artifacts can interfere with feature detection by mimicking the pigment network and interfering with accurate border detection [16]. Lama et al. utilized this novel architecture to outperform the standard UNet and UResNet architectures used in state-of-the-art hair and ruler detection and segmentation results. They note that their approach improved the Jaccard score by 10% from 0.59 to 0.65 and the Dice score by 6.9% from 0.72 to 0.77 compared with the U-Net, and it also improved the Jaccard score by 3.2% from 0.63 to 0.65 and the precision by 2.6% from 0.77 to 0.79 as compared with the UResNet. Despite promising results, Lama et al. concluded their work by pointing to the disadvantages of their proposed technique – the large number of images and image masks required for training, validation, and testing (in their case totaling 1333 images), which required hundreds of hours to generate. The progression of research in hair and ruler instance segmentation would appear to hinge on creating an open-access dataset for images and pixel annotations.

Distributed Computation:

Concerns about computational limits and data privacy have driven substantial research in distributed computation. Here, distributed computation is the process of decentralizing computation by allowing collaborators to train models on small non-overlapping partitions of the data and synthesizing model parameters across the collaborative network. One unique feature of this computing paradigm is that it allows for differential access to data by each computational unit within a computer network, facilitating data privacy and security. However, in the case of machine learning, distributed computing faces challenges owing to information sharing: it is difficult for models trained on independent nodes to share the same parameters, and communication costs are associated with sharing this information over a network. Nonetheless, distributed computation has been utilized in the medical setting to expedite computationally heavy work streams while ensuring data is encrypted and privatized. Islam et al., for example, developed an IoMT-assisted framework for remote data collection, secure data transmission, and cloud storage [9]. They used local data collection devices (i.e., Raspberry Pi Camera) that send data to central data storage. From this point, data is utilized to train deep learning models via cloud computation. They managed to train ensemble deep learning models with high accuracy even while validated on skin images collected at home by patients using smart devices. Their ensemble model achieved a test accuracy and an AUC-ROC of 0.87 and 0.97, respectively.

Joshi et al. explored federated learning, a paradigm in which a machine learning algorithm is trained across multiple decentralized devices or servers holding local data samples [8]. Based on known split-fed (SFL) and multi-head split-fed learning (MHSFL) methods for model training that preserve patient data security, Joshi et al. compared the accuracy and information leakage achieved by models trained under each protocol. They found that while models trained under SFL paradigms achieve higher accuracy than those trained under MHSFL, information leakage – measured by the mutual information score – is considerably greater under SFL conditions than MHSFL conditions, particularly under conditions of high-dataset complexity (e.g., RGB images). These results are likely explained by the client-side model synchronization that occurs in SFL that does not in MHSFL. They also note that for healthcare-based datasets (i.e., ECG, HAM-10000, etc...). SFL was seen to be marginally better than MHSFL, though they offer few explanations regarding why this might be. Finally, due to their varied test configurations, Joshi et al. showed that having a higher number of layers within the client-side model resulted in improved performance for SFL, while increasing the number of client-side layers led to a deterioration in the performance of MHSFL.

Image Synthesis:

The HAM10000 dataset has also furthered research efforts in synthetic image generation, which is uniquely positioned to alleviate concerns about dataset diversity (e.g., underrepresentation of certain disease types). However, one issue with synthetic image generation has been limitations in generated content, i.e., disease type, image style, orientation, lighting, etc. Whereas content can be manipulated using conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN), style-related modifications have been more elusive. However, Havaei et al., used the HAM10000 dataset to train a modified cGAN that disentangles image content from image style [20]. Leveraging a dual adversarial inference framework, they trained a model that beats SOTA considerably, achieving a Frechet Inception Distance (FID) of 1.2 (compared to SOTA at 1.3), a near 10% improvement. Moreover, they achieved significantly lower disentanglement error than other baselines, indicating the importance of dual adversarial inference, which can separate style from content. To address the problems of insufficient data samples and sample imbalance in training datasets, Li et al. performed dermoscopy dataset augmentation based on generative adversarial networks [7]. Their GAN, which utilized standard binary cross-entropy loss, differed from traditional GANs in that it incorporated channel and spatial attention on the generator side. This modification substantially increased the quality of generated images and may be worth adopting more generally. Their diverse data augmentation generative adversarial network (DDA-GAN) policy considerably increased image classification performance when comparing the standard test dataset with the augmented test dataset (i.e., their InceptionV3 performance on the test set was 0.86, 0.88, 0.87, 0.87 before augmentation, and 0.95, 0.96, 0.95, 0.96 after augmentation, in accuracy, precision, recall, and F1, respectively.)

User-Centered Design:

Due to the technical expertise requirements, most deep learning algorithms are developed by experts with computer science backgrounds. Moreover, even those with technical competence may not understand broader epidemiological considerations and sources of information bias (e.g., confounding, batch effects, etc...). As such, several automated deep learning platforms have been developed to perform neural architecture searches, thus lowering barriers to entry for non-experts. Faes et al. examined whether healthcare professionals could utilize such platforms with little to no technical understanding of machine learning [29]. In their study, two physicians with no coding or machine learning experience developed models using Google Cloud AutoML. Their results suggest that providers with no coding expertise can develop deep learning models via automated deep learning platforms with performance comparable to SOTA baselines in binary classification tasks (sensitivity: 0.73-0.97; specificity: 0.67-1.00), though the performance of these models is less impressive in the multi-class setting (sensitivity: 0.38-1.00; specificity: 0.67-1.00), where they found that computational expertise becomes more crucial [29].

Validation:

Finally, validation studies aim to examine the performance of common deep learning models in diverse clinical settings outside of the context where they were originally developed. For example, real-world image artifacts may considerably attenuate model performance. Katsch et al. analyzed the performance of deep learning models trained on the HAM10000 dataset against images with common artifacts like skin and ruler markings [5]. In their study, they trained models like ResNet-34, Faster R-CNN, and Mask R-CNN on HAM10000 images without image artifacts, and tested their performance on HAM10000 images with artifacts. They found that all models trained on regular images perform worse on images with superimposed artifacts [5]. Artifacts in testing images decreased AUC-ROC values of 0.030 for ResNet-34 and 0.045 for Faster R-CNN and 0.011 for Mask R-CNN, likely due to limitations in model generalization. More generally, Combalia et al. attempted to validate several deep learning models against clinically realistic scenarios, such as viewing images outside of the categories provided in training. In this study, researchers created a grand challenge to which 64 teams submitted 129 SOTA algorithm predictions on a test set of 8238 images [17]. This challenge was structured so teams were given 25331 images from the HAM10000 and BCN20000 datasets. A separate test dataset included 8238, of which many images belonged to disease categories not represented in the training set. They found that median balanced accuracy on the HAM10000, BCN20000 without new labels, and BCN20000 with new labels were 0.68, 0.49, and 0.42, respectively, illustrating a massive decrease in performance from training settings to more realistic settings [17]. More concerningly, novel categories provided at testing time were frequently benign, however, they were confused for malignancy 47% of the time by the top 25 algorithms, representing a significant limitation for clinical implementation [17]. This has concerning implications for applying these algorithms in the clinical setting, where there is a significant risk for misdiagnosis – and, more specifically, malignant misdiagnosis – which may incur additional costs to the patient and clinician.

Key Takeaways

From this discussion, we have compiled a list of key takeaways which summarize the major contributions from recent works as well as recommendations for future advances:

- **Classification:** A range of diverse preprocessing strategies, feature extraction approaches, and model architectures were leveraged. While most studies successfully utilized standard image augmentation, GAN augmentation was especially successful at reducing dataset imbalance. For feature extraction, the most successful methods applied attention-based approaches at different image scales to capture salient information at different levels of granularity. While model architectures were varied, the best performing architectures leveraged attention mechanisms and transformer architectures. One limitation of these models is that they may not have accessible pre-trained weights for transfer learning, shown to be incredibly productive in this domain. Therefore, researchers producing novel architectures may consider publishing their model and its weights to expand access to TL even for novel models. Finally, model ensembles were observed to improve performance at the expense of training and inference times, which presents a challenge to their wide-spread clinical application. Future research may focus on reducing the computational overhead associated with ensemble models.
- **Segmentation:** Research in image segmentation has greatly benefited from the HAM10000 dataset. Authors have demonstrated the global utility of incorporating both spatial and channel attention into segmentation models; therefore, future work in segmentation may benefit from incorporating both attention modules into baseline model architecture. Research in artifact removal has demonstrated the tenability of VAE in image denoising. Moreover, reduced synthetic image quality may be attenuated via incorporation of perceptual loss. Jointly, these results show that VAE might be a fruitful approach to remove artifacts of other kinds (i.e., ruler marks), and that some of the drawbacks of generative approaches like these can be mitigated through clever loss functions. Finally, creating a paired image and image mask dataset is costly and time-consuming. Therefore, curating an open-access dataset containing skin images with hair and ruler marks, and corresponding image masks, will be critical for future research.
- **Distributed Computing:** Modern distributed computation approaches continue to explore the optimal tradeoff between data privacy and model performance. As progress continues, healthcare research will benefit from adopting distributed computing paradigms, especially to alleviate data privacy concerns. Moreover, it has been shown that model performance and data privacy can be pursued simultaneously, as in the case of MHSFL, a brand of federated learning. More work, however, needs to be done to elucidate precisely which federated learning schemes work best for different settings, and why these schemes have differential performances – as different schemes will cater to different tasks.
- **Image Synthesis:** Synthetic image generation is poised to be an invaluable asset in pursuing dataset diversification in medical computer vision (i.e., underrepresented

disease populations). Moreover, synthesis methods that allow for the manipulation of both style and content can allow for this goal to be effectively achieved. However, it is presently unknown the extent to which changes in style might help in dataset augmentation. Therefore, further work should seek to quantitatively evaluate the advantages variations in style can provide in the augmentation of training datasets for image classifiers.

- **User Centered Design:** Low/no-code machine learning platforms have shown great promise in the medical setting. However, the limitations facing these platforms (e.g., performance in the multi-class classification setting, and relatively low customizability) reaffirm the importance of AI literacy and technical competence in healthcare spaces. Future work should attempt to further study the utility of these low/no-code ML platforms in tasks outside of classification, such as image segmentation, or synthetic image generation. Moreover, collaborations between clinicians and machines remain woefully understudied, though platforms such as these may facilitate, for example, expert-in-the-loop style training.
- **Validation:** Validation studies utilizing the HAM10000 dataset have highlighted the need for high-quality, diverse image datasets. As image artifacts can considerably decrease the performance of image segmentation models, efforts must be coordinated to increase the quality of image datasets and make these models more resilient to such artifacts, potentially through denoising algorithms. Similarly, as SOTA classification models generalize poorly on novel datasets and tend to classify unknown disorders as malignant more frequently than benign, researchers must focus on training models that generalize more robustly. Synthetic image generation methods that increase the representation of underrepresented samples may be apt for this task.

Conclusion:

The HAM10000 dataset provides public open-source access to a rich, high quality dermoscopic imaging dataset, which has been used to demonstrate the performance of SOTA deep learning models for various computer vision tasks, including classification, segmentation, distributed computation, and image synthesis. This scoping systematic review touched on elements which remain crucial for developing effective deep learning models for dermatological images– 1) attention matters as well as manually segmenting areas of interest prior to classification, 2) transfer learning often provide additional performance gains versus model architecture changes, and there are several 3) validation and 4) user-centered design challenges which must be addressed prior to widespread implementation. Taken together, balancing clinical intuition with technical quantitative expertise and addressing these challenges can lead to the development of more accurate and clinically useful deep learning models for dermatological images.

References:

- [1] M. Karri, C. S. R. Annavarapu, and U. R. Acharya, "Explainable multi-module semantic guided attention based network for medical image segmentation," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 151, p. 106231, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compbimed.2022.106231.
- [2] S. S. Samsudin, H. Arof, S. W. Harun, A. W. Abdul Wahab, and M. Y. I. Idris, "Skin lesion classification using multi-resolution empirical mode decomposition and local binary pattern," *PLoS One*, vol. 17, no. 9, p. e0274896, 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0274896.
- [3] H. C. Reis, V. Turk, K. Khoshelham, and S. Kaya, "InSiNet: a deep convolutional approach to skin cancer detection and segmentation," *Med Biol Eng Comput*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 643–662, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11517-021-02473-0.
- [4] S. Qian, K. Ren, W. Zhang, and H. Ning, "Skin lesion classification using CNNs with grouping of multi-scale attention and class-specific loss weighting," *Comput Methods Programs Biomed*, vol. 226, p. 107166, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.107166.
- [5] F. Katsch, C. Rinner, and P. Tschandl, "Comparison of Convolutional Neural Network Architectures for Robustness Against Common Artefacts in Dermatoscopic Images," *Dermatol Pract Concept*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. e2022126, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.5826/dpc.1203a126.
- [6] C. Xin *et al.*, "An improved transformer network for skin cancer classification," *Comput Biol Med*, vol. 149, p. 105939, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compbimed.2022.105939.
- [7] H. Li, W. Li, J. Chang, L. Zhou, J. Luo, and Y. Guo, "Dermoscopy lesion classification based on GANs and a fuzzy rank-based ensemble of CNN models," *Phys. Med. Biol.*, vol. 67, no. 18, p. 185005, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac8b60.
- [8] P. Joshi, C. Thapa, S. Camtepe, M. Hasanuzzaman, T. Scully, and H. Afli, "Performance and Information Leakage in Splitfed Learning and Multi-Head Split Learning in Healthcare Data and Beyond," *Methods Protoc*, vol. 5, no. 4, p. 60, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/mps5040060.
- [9] M. K. Islam *et al.*, "A Secure Framework toward IoMT-Assisted Data Collection, Modeling, and Classification for Intelligent Dermatology Healthcare Services," *Contrast Media Mol Imaging*, vol. 2022, p. 6805460, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/6805460.
- [10] D. Popescu, M. El-khatib, and L. Ichim, "Skin Lesion Classification Using Collective Intelligence of Multiple Neural Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 12, Art. no. 12, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22124399.
- [11] S. Aladhadh, M. Alsanea, M. Aloraini, T. Khan, S. Habib, and M. Islam, "An Effective Skin Cancer Classification Mechanism via Medical Vision Transformer," *Sensors (Basel)*, vol. 22, no. 11, p. 4008, May 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22114008.
- [12] D. Bardou, H. Bouaziz, L. Lv, and T. Zhang, "Hair removal in dermoscopy images using variational autoencoders," *Skin Research and Technology*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 445–454, 2022, doi: 10.1111/srt.13145.
- [13] F. Afza, M. Sharif, M. A. Khan, U. Tariq, H.-S. Yong, and J. Cha, "Multiclass Skin Lesion Classification Using Hybrid Deep Features Selection and Extreme Learning Machine," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 3, Art. no. 3, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22030799.
- [14] S. Wang, Y. Yin, D. Wang, Y. Wang, and Y. Jin, "Interpretability-Based Multimodal Convolutional Neural Networks for Skin Lesion Diagnosis," *IEEE Trans Cybern*, vol. PP, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TCYB.2021.3069920.
- [15] N. Mohanty, M. Pradhan, A. V. N. Reddy, S. Kumar, and A. Alkhayyat, "Integrated Design of Optimized Weighted Deep Feature Fusion Strategies for Skin Lesion Image

- Classification,” *Cancers (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 22, p. 5716, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/cancers14225716.
- [16] N. Lama *et al.*, “ChimeraNet: U-Net for Hair Detection in Dermoscopic Skin Lesion Images,” *J Digit Imaging*, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10278-022-00740-6.
- [17] M. Combalia *et al.*, “Validation of artificial intelligence prediction models for skin cancer diagnosis using dermoscopy images: the 2019 International Skin Imaging Collaboration Grand Challenge,” *The Lancet Digital Health*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. e330–e339, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/S2589-7500(22)00021-8.
- [18] S. A. Thomas, “Combining Image Features and Patient Metadata to Enhance Transfer Learning,” Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630047.
- [19] S. Jain, U. Singhania, B. Tripathy, E. A. Nasr, M. K. Aboudaif, and A. K. Kamrani, “Deep Learning-Based Transfer Learning for Classification of Skin Cancer,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, Art. no. 23, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21238142.
- [20] M. Havaei, X. Mao, Y. Wang, and Q. Lao, “Conditional generation of medical images via disentangled adversarial inference,” *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 72, p. 102106, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.media.2021.102106.
- [21] M. A. Khan, K. Muhammad, M. Sharif, T. Akram, and V. H. C. de Albuquerque, “Multi-Class Skin Lesion Detection and Classification via Teledermatology,” *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*, vol. 25, no. 12, pp. 4267–4275, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2021.3067789.
- [22] M. A. Khan, M. Sharif, T. Akram, R. Damaševičius, and R. Maskeliūnas, “Skin Lesion Segmentation and Multiclass Classification Using Deep Learning Features and Improved Moth Flame Optimization,” *Diagnostics (Basel)*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 811, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics11050811.
- [23] P. N. Srinivasu, J. G. SivaSai, M. F. Ijaz, A. K. Bhoi, W. Kim, and J. J. Kang, “Classification of Skin Disease Using Deep Learning Neural Networks with MobileNet V2 and LSTM,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 8, Art. no. 8, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21082852.
- [24] H.-W. Huang, B. W.-Y. Hsu, C.-H. Lee, and V. S. Tseng, “Development of a light-weight deep learning model for cloud applications and remote diagnosis of skin cancers,” *The Journal of Dermatology*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 310–316, 2021, doi: 10.1111/1346-8138.15683.
- [25] A. A., “A Deep Learning Approach to Skin Cancer Detection in Dermoscopy Images,” *J Biomed Phys Eng*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 801–806, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.31661/jbpe.v0i0.2004-1107.
- [26] C. B. Hansen *et al.*, “Semi-supervised Machine Learning with MixMatch and Equivalence Classes,” *Lect Notes Monogr Ser*, vol. 12446, pp. 112–121, 2020.
- [27] J. Allyn, N. Allou, C. Vidal, A. Renou, and C. Ferdynus, “Adversarial attack on deep learning-based dermatoscopic image recognition systems,” *Medicine (Baltimore)*, vol. 99, no. 50, p. e23568, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000023568.
- [28] L. Wang *et al.*, “AK-DL: A Shallow Neural Network Model for Diagnosing Actinic Keratosis with Better Performance Than Deep Neural Networks,” *Diagnostics (Basel)*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 217, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics10040217.
- [29] L. Faes *et al.*, “Automated deep learning design for medical image classification by health-care professionals with no coding experience: a feasibility study,” *The Lancet Digital Health*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. e232–e242, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/S2589-7500(19)30108-6.
- [30] A. Mobiny, A. Singh, and H. Van Nguyen, “Risk-Aware Machine Learning Classifier for Skin Lesion Diagnosis,” *J Clin Med*, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 1241, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.3390/jcm8081241.

- [31] P. Tschandl, C. Rosendahl, and H. Kittler, "The HAM10000 dataset, a large collection of multi-source dermatoscopic images of common pigmented skin lesions," *Sci Data*, vol. 5, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2018.161.
- [32] H. K. Jeong, C. Park, R. Henao, and M. Kheterpal, "Deep Learning in Dermatology: a systematic review of current approaches, outcomes and limitations," *JID Innovations*, p. 100150, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.xjidi.2022.100150.
- [33] A. Dosovitskiy *et al.*, "An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale." arXiv, Jun. 03, 2021. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2010.11929.
- [34] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition." arXiv, Dec. 10, 2015. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1512.03385.
- [35] M. Tan and Q. V. Le, "EfficientNet: Rethinking Model Scaling for Convolutional Neural Networks." arXiv, Sep. 11, 2020. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1905.11946.
- [36] J. Kato, K. Horimoto, S. Sato, T. Minowa, and H. Uhara, "Dermoscopy of Melanoma and Non-melanoma Skin Cancers," *Front Med (Lausanne)*, vol. 6, p. 180, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fmed.2019.00180.
- [37] T. Mendonca *et al.*, "Comparison of segmentation methods for automatic diagnosis of dermoscopy images," *Annu Int Conf IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc*, vol. 2007, pp. 6573–6576, 2007, doi: 10.1109/IEMBS.2007.4353865.
- [38] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher, L.-J. Li, K. Li, and L. Fei-Fei, "ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database," in *2009 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Jun. 2009, pp. 248–255. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2009.5206848.
- [39] R. Bai and M. Zhou, "SL-HarDNet: Skin lesion segmentation with HarDNet," *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, vol. 10, 2023, Accessed: Feb. 26, 2023, doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2022.1028690.
- [40] T. H. H. Aldhyani, A. Verma, M. H. Al-Adhaileh, and D. Koundal, "Multi-Class Skin Lesion Classification Using a Lightweight Dynamic Kernel Deep-Learning-Based Convolutional Neural Network," *Diagnostics (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. 2048, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics12092048.
- [41] M. Arshad *et al.*, "A Computer-Aided Diagnosis System Using Deep Learning for Multiclass Skin Lesion Classification," *Comput Intell Neurosci*, vol. 2021, p. 9619079, 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/9619079.
- [42] T. M. Alam *et al.*, "An Efficient Deep Learning-Based Skin Cancer Classifier for an Imbalanced Dataset," *Diagnostics (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. 2115, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics12092115.
- [43] N. Girdhar, A. Sinha, and S. Gupta, "DenseNet-II: an improved deep convolutional neural network for melanoma cancer detection," *Soft comput*, pp. 1–20, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s00500-022-07406-z.
- [44] I. Loshchilov and F. Hutter, "SGDR: Stochastic Gradient Descent with Warm Restarts." arXiv, May 03, 2017. Accessed: Feb. 26, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.03983>

Supplementary Materials:

Excluded studies: Four studies were excluded during the eligibility evaluation stage due to biased training and evaluation methodologies, corresponding to exclusion criteria 4A and 4B. In all, two general types of flaws were observed. These flaws included overlapping training/testing sets [40]–[42], and the potential for duplicate images to present in the test set [43]. Three studies utilized image augmentation practices to synthesize additional images for training and testing. However, the augmented images were partitioned randomly into the training and testing sets, disregarding the corresponding source image, resulting in images in the test dataset derived from images in the training dataset. Aldhyani et al., Arshad et al., and Alam et al. utilized image augmentation to increase the number of samples in all classes to 6500, 6000, and 4000–5000 images respectively in a class-specific manner [40]–[42]. Then, the augmented data was included in partitioned training/testing/validation cohorts. As augmented images from the same source image were randomly partitioned into different cohorts, some of the testing set images were derived from training set images. This can potentially inflate performance on the test set as we expect the model to perform well on the training set by inducing correlations between training and test set characteristics. In particular, a base/training image X might have been augmented by two separate augmentations, $T1$ and $T2$, into $X'=T1(X)$ and $X''=T2(X)$. Both X' and X'' may be partitioned to the test set using the approach taken by the authors. If X is in the training set, then having both X' and X'' in the test represents information leakage that may jeopardize test performance. Second, one study produced testing cohorts that potentially contained duplicate images as a function of their augmentation protocol [40]–[43]. Performance evaluation on a set of this sort is largely unrepresentative of real-world performance. Together, these practices produced training/testing/validation cohorts liable to performance overinflation. Thus, on account of these two methodological errors, these studies were not included in the final analysis.

Model ensembles may outperform single-network approaches: Ensemble models improved performance in classification tasks over their single-network counterparts. These gains are partly due to the advantages of ensemble models over single models in training, where ensembling can work synergistically with stochastic gradient descent with warm restarts [44]. Li et al. developed a fuzzy rank-based ensemble multilayer feature fusion CNN model, reaching an accuracy and F1-score of 0.96 and 0.96, respectively [7]. This constituted a near 0.1 improvement over the SOTA single model performance they cite in their paper. Popescu et al. also leveraged an ensemble-based method where unique weights were learned for each constituent model. In their study, ensemble methods reached an accuracy of 0.867, a 0.02 increase from the highest-performing individual model [10].

As such, adopting model ensembles may represent a way to improve performance on the HAM1000 classification task. However, these ensemble models typically take much longer to train and test, which presents challenges to wide-scale clinical application. Therefore, future research may focus on reducing the computational overhead associated with ensemble models.

Authors	Model Architecture	Description
Samsudin et al., [2].	Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	“The input layer has 512 nodes to cater for the LBP features from the original image and its first BIMF. The hidden layer has 25 neurons while output layer has 7 neurons which matches the number of lesion classes” [2].
Qian et al., [4]	ResNet50 and grouping of multi-scale attention blocks (GMAB)	The ResNet50 model is used as the model backbone, however all convolutional layers are replaced with GMAB layers. Specifically, every “conv” layer is replaced with the following series of kernels: [1x1, GMAB, 1x1] x n, where n varies by the layer. An adaptive loss function is also utilized [4].
Xin et al., [6].	Vision Transformer (ViT) + MLP	“Compared with the traditional vision transformer (ViT) model, a multi-scale vision transformer mainly improves the image feature embedding module and applies the contrastive learning method to the skin cancer classification” [6].
Li et al., [7]	GAN, Ensemble of Xception, DenseNet121 and InceptionV3	“A fuzzy rank-based ensemble of multilayer feature fusion CNN models is proposed to classify skin by integrating the classification results via fuzzy rank, which can enhance the generalization capability of the CNN model, and improve network stability and classification accuracy” [7]. Additionally, Li et al. designed an efficient channel integrating spatial attention (ECISA) module for capturing meaningful multiscale features from the enlarged receptive field. They incorporate this module into both the generator and discriminator of the GAN, and within the Xception, DenseNet121 and InceptionV3 models.
Popescu et al., [10].	Ensemble	“In the proposed system we used 9 NNs considered as individual intelligent classifiers. These networks (AlexNet, GoogLeNet, GoogLeNet-Places365, ResNet-50, ResNet-101, Xception, MobileNet-V2, DenseNet-201, and InceptionResNet-V2) will be the backbone of the collective intelligence system” [10]. The final decision for the ensemble is computed via a decision matrix based on adaptive weights.
Aladhadh et al., [11].	Medical Vision Transformer (MVT)	Input layer receives 72 by 72-pixel image, which is then split into patches. There is an embedding layer, an encoding layer, and a classification layer [11].
Afza et al., [13].	NASNET Large	“The input size of image for the NasNet Large is 331-by-331. A child network of unique structure is created in NAS by the recurrent neural network (RNN). The child networks are trained using a holdout method to achieve accuracy. The controller is updated using the combined accuracy of child networks to create a better architecture for the network. The controller predictions are gathered into A blocks. Five unique SoftMax classifiers make five predictions at five steps of the block in accordance with the discrete choices of blocks” [13].
Wang et al., [14].	IM-CNN	Wang et al. combined three distinct streams of information (i.e., metadata, image features, and segmented information) together into a multimodal embedding, before feeding this embedding into a final output layer. The metadata and image features are passed through a catboost model (decision tree boosting), while the segmented image is passed through the EfficientNetB5 model [14].
Mohanty et al., [15].	VGG16, EfficientNet B0, and ResNet50 + Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, Multi-Layer Perceptron, and Support Vector Machine classifiers	Mohanty et al., use various CNNs to generate image embeddings, before using HWO to enhance these embeddings. Afterwards a decision tree, naive bayes classifier, MLP, and SVM are used for classification [15].
Thomas [18].	Alexnet, Resnet50, GoogleNet, VGG16, DenseNet201, InceptionResNetV2	Images are fed through these CNNs in the traditional way up until the final global pooling layer. After this layer, the subsequent image embedding is fused with a metadata embedding, before being passed to the final fully connected layer [18].
Jain et al., [19].	VGG19, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, Resnet50, Xception. and MobileNet.	Transfer learning was utilized to initialize these models with weights. One additional fully connected layer was added to produce final class predictions [19].

Khan et al., [22].	ResNet101, DenseNet201 + Kernel Extreme Learning Machine (KELM)	CNNs were used to generate feature embeddings for each image. After a series of feature selection techniques, the final refined embedding was passed to the KELM for prediction [22].
Khan et al., [21].	16-layer CNN, DenseNet, Extreme Learning Machine	Lesion segmentation is performed by the 16-layer CNN in conjunction with a modified HDCT saliency approach. These masks are combined using a maximum mutual information (MMI) approach. A DenseNet CNN was utilized for feature extraction. [21]
Srinivasu et al., [23].	MobileNet V2 model + LSTM	MobileNet V2 is used in classifying the type of skin disease, and LSTM is used to enhance the performance of the model by maintaining the state information of the features that it comes across in the previous generation of the image classification [23].
Huang et al., [24].	EfficientNet and DenseNet121	Both models were used with standard configurations except the final layer was modified to predict seven and two classes, respectively [24].
Ameri [25].	AlexNet	Standard configuration utilizing TL. Input size was 227 by 227 [25].
Hansen et al., [26].	Four-layer FCNN	Four-layer FCNN with approximately 300,000 total parameters. Model was initialized with weights from the 2017 Data Science Bowl lung cancer diagnosis challenge [26].
Allyn et al., [27].	DenseNet-201	Standard configuration, with TL from ImageNet. Output layer was modified per the task [27].
Mobiny et al., [30].	VGG-16, ResNet-50, and DenseNet-169 with bayesian module	“The standard DenseNet-169 network is composed of four Dense Blocks (DB) with a growth rate of 32. Each DB is followed by a convolution and average pooling pairs which together compress the information by reducing the spatial dimension and number of feature maps by half. The four DBs are composed of 6, 12, 32, and 32 bottleneck blocks, respectively. The bottleneck block...includes two convolution layers with filter sizes of 1 and 3, respectively. A global average pooling layer is used after the last DB, followed by fully-connected layers with, respectively, 128 and 7 (the total number of classes) units” [30].

Supplementary Table 1: Model Architecture by Study. A range of distinct architectures were leveraged across the classification task. The multiclass classification architectures are detailed here.

Authors	Augmentation Strategy	Data Balancing
Samsudin et al., [2].	<i>Did not report data augmentation.</i>	Balanced training data by sampling the same number of images from each class.
Qian et al., [4].	Standard augmentation, including horizontal/vertical flip, random rotation, and cutout.	Oversampling method.
Xin et al., [6].	Standard augmentation, including horizontal/vertical flip, random crop, random rotation, color jitter.	Balanced sampling.
Li et al., [7].	GAN Augmentation.	Produced synthetic images to balance data.

Popescu et al., [10].	Standard augmentation including shearing, rotations (on both vertical and horizontal axis), flip, random image zoom, and vertical or horizontal pixel shift.	Data augmentation used to increase the size of minority classes.
Aladhadh et al., [11].	Standard augmentation including horizontal/vertical flip, random rotation, brightness enhancement, and contrast enhancement.	Augmentation applied only to the minority classes.
Afza et al., [13].	Contrast enhancement.	Data balancing was also performed on each class.
Wang et al., [14].	Standard augmentation, including random rotations, random horizontal and vertical flips, random width or height shifting, and zooming and shearing. Further color, brightness, and contrast augmentation was performed.	Used augmentation to equalize the number of images in each class.
Mohanty et al., [15].	<i>Did not report data augmentation.</i>	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Thomas [18].	Standard augmentation, including random shift, random rotation, and random horizontal/vertical flips.	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Jain et al., [19].	Standard augmentation, including rotation, zooming, and vertical/horizontal shift.	Replicated images for low sample classes
Khan et al., [22]	The authors state that data augmentation is performed. Unclear what kind.	Augmentation was used to increase the number of images
Srinivasu et al., [23].	Standard augmentation, including rotations and transformation.	The also used augmentation to improve data imbalance

Huang et al., [24].	<i>Did not report data augmentation.</i>	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Khan et al., [21].	<i>Did not report data augmentation.</i>	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Ameri [25].	<i>Did not report data augmentation.</i>	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Hansen et al., [26].	Unique augmentation	Unique balancing
Allyn et al., [27].	Standard augmentation techniques, including rotation and cropping were used.	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>
Mobiny et al., [30].	Standard augmentation, including random horizontal/vertical flips, image shifts, random changes to brightness and saturation, and random rotation.	<i>Did not report data balancing.</i>

Supplementary Table 2: Image Augmentation and Data Balancing Strategies by Multiclass Classification Study. All 19 multiclass classification studies were analyzed for image augmentation and data balancing strategies. 14 studies reported some form of image augmentation, while 12 studies reported some form of data balancing.